

Conference Abstract

Biogeochemical reactivity in the unsaturated zone revealed by in-situ measurements

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Abstract

Bedrock mineral breakdown in mountainous landscapes sustains long-term atmospheric CO₂ drawdown and releases solutes that sustain ecosystems and set the chemistry of upland stream water. In the unsaturated Bedrock Vadose Zone (BVZ) of hillslopes, minerals, water, reactive gases, and deep roots interact to produce a hotspot of these weathering reactions. New evidence suggests that, in the BVZ, rock moisture sustains evapotranspiration, while deep roots drive deep CO₂ production. However, the contribution of the BVZ to catchment-scale chemical weathering fluxes, and particularly the role of deep roots as drivers of this reactivity, remains poorly constrained due to the difficulty of direct access and measurement of fluids in this compartment. Quantifying this BVZ chemical reactivity is crucial to advance our understanding of upland landscapes' influence on the global carbon cycle and river solute fluxes. Here, we leverage an innovative Vadose-zone Monitoring System (VMS) to investigate these processes and their biogeochemical implications.

We present four years of in-situ monitoring of water and pore gas composition in a ~16-meter weathered bedrock profile at the Eel River Critical Zone Observatory (ERCZO) in California. Using this novel instrumentation, we show that the average geogenic chemical solute efflux from the BVZ is $80 \pm 34 \text{ t km}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, representing approximately 68% of the solute flux measured in the creek draining the hillslope. This highlights the

substantial role of the BVZ in catchment-scale weathering. To further interpret these data, we develop a multi-component reactive transport model (RTM) calibrated with batch-reactor experiments using drilling cuttings from the hillslope. Results indicate that solute concentrations arise from a coupled set of primary mineral dissolution and secondary mineral precipitation reactions, which evolve with depth and align with the mineralogical composition gradient from soil to fresh bedrock. Our RTM demonstrates that water storage and drainage timescales in the vadose zone are sufficient to allow significant evolution of pore water due to chemical weathering. However, the model cannot reproduce observed solute concentrations unless elevated CO₂ from deep rhizosphere respiration is incorporated. We find that organic carbon respiration in the deep rhizosphere enhances chemical weathering fluxes at the ERCZO by a factor of $\sim 1.8 \pm 0.5$, providing direct evidence of accelerated chemical weathering in the Critical Zone due to the presence and function of deeply rooted vegetation.

A key characteristic of the linkage between deep rhizosphere respiration and weathering reactions is that, despite strong seasonal variations in water content and O₂ profiles, CO₂ concentrations in the BVZ remain stable, leading to steady weathering rates across seasons and years. Sensitivity analyses with our calibrated RTM reveal that this stability results from the interplay between labile organic carbon oxidation and seasonal hydrological conditions. During dry periods, O₂ is abundant throughout the BVZ due to opening of pore space, but DOC availability is constrained by low water content. Conversely, wet periods enhance availability of labile organic carbon, but O₂ becomes limiting. This balance maintains stable CO₂ profiles and, ultimately, steady weathering rates. We propose that this buffering mechanism allows watersheds to modulate seasonal variability in ecological, hydrological, and climatic inputs, contributing to the pervasive observation of stable concentrations of geogenic solutes in streams draining these landscapes despite their strong variations in discharge. These findings underscore the critical role of the BVZ in regulating solute fluxes from hillslopes, and suggest that deep vadose zone processes must be integrated into biogeochemical and hydrological models to accurately predict catchment responses to environmental change.

Keywords

vadose zone geochemistry, chemical weathering, deep rhizosphere, critical zone

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.